

Diabetic foot prevention from amputation with epidermal growth factor: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT Diabetic foot is a common complication of diabetes mellitus, and it is the most common cause of foot amputations worldwide. Coordinating patient care with other specialists, using new treatment technology and including the patient as a significant part of the team are all required for effective patient care. In this case report, we wanted to show the results of epidermal growth factor which was recently introduced in our patient with a diabetic foot ulcer. A male patient age 65, it was observed that the ulcer area was reduced with the epidermal growth factor and the recovery was faster. By using epidermal growth factor, the rate of secondary complication is reduced, and the patient is protected from amputation.

KEYWORDS diabetic foot, wound healing, epidermal growth factor

Introduction

Diabetic foot ulcers are among essential conditions to be highlighted because they may cause serious problems extending to significant amputation of extremities.[1] Diabetic foot ulcers are developed due to isolated or combined effects of peripheral neuropathy, vascular insufficiency, infection and immune system disorders.[2,3] The foot with complete loss of sensation becomes prone to ulceration because repetitive trauma cannot be perceived and protective measures are not taken. Diabetic foot lesions lead to a wide spectrum of conditions starting from simple superficial hyperemia to ulceration, osteomyelitis and gangrene. Although ulceration may occur on every region of the foot, it is most frequently seen on the plantar forefoot. [4] The risk of foot ulcer and extremity amputation increases with age and duration of diabetes. [5,6] Prevention of diabetic foot is crucial regarding both the quality of life of patients and the economic burden of this condition on the healthcare system. Here we present a patient who applied to our polyclinic because of a diabetic foot wound. We wanted to share the results of

epidermal growth factor in non-healing diabetic foot ulcers and the results of our patient with our colleagues.

Case Report

A male patient aged sixty-five applied to our polyclinic with the complaint of diabetic foot ulcer wound sized approximately 7x12cm on the front face of the right foot. The patient had been given hyperbaric oxygen treatment for three months in a different centre, and at the end of the treatment he was recommended amputation. He did not accept amputation and applied to us. Upon examination, it was seen that the wound was clean (figure 1 and 2), and there was no osteomyelitis developed as determined by radiography. Thus the Epidermal Growth Factor (EGF) application was decided. The patient was hospitalised and a treatment consisting of daily wound debridement and intralesional EGF 3 times a week for three months was given (figure 3,4 and 5). At the end of 3 months, the patient was discharged with his foot wound healed and almost completely closed.

Discussion

Diabetes is the most common cause of foot amputations. Fifty-one percent of the lower extremity amputations are diabetes-related. Amputation rate increases with advancing age and is greater in males.[7] Foot ulcers are among the most significant causes for hospitalisation of diabetic patients and are related to high morbidity and mortality as well as severe problems for

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Figure 1. The wound was clean.

Figure 2. After two weeks, EGF intralesional administration.

Figure 3. Wound healing at the end of the first month.

Figure 4. At the end of 2 months, the wound is about to close.

Figure 5. After three months, the wound is completely healing.

patients and their families. Patients living dependent on their caregivers throughout the treatment and the very high costs of the treatment give rise to socioeconomic concerns. The average cost of a treatment of a hospitalized patient with a diabetic foot ulcer in the U.S. was estimated at 36,000 dollars.[8] The reported diabetic ulcer healing rates ranged from 33 to 57.5% at a cutoff time of 12–20 weeks, when the growth factors PDGF or FGF were used in controlled trials. In a small pilot randomized double-blind study reported by Richard et al., nine chronic neuropathic plantar foot ulcers (Wegner grade I–III) were treated with topical FGF for a total of 18 weeks. The healing rates for the treated and placebo group were 33 and 63%, respectively, with no statistically significant difference. In a large multicenter study, PDGF, at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in cream, gave a better healing rate (50%) than the placebo group (35%) in a 20-week study ($P = 0.007$).[9,10] In a randomized double-blind study by Montequin et al., intralesional Heberprot-P was administered three times

a week at a dose of 75 mcg to one group and a dose of 25mcgr to another group. Granulation response as complete response following intralesional EGF administration was 73.9% in the first group (75mcgr) and 50% in the second group (25mcgr) at the end of 5 weeks. The complete response rate was 82.6% in the first group and 61.1% in the second group at eight weeks. [11]

Diabetic foot ulcers should be carefully evaluated, and the gold-standard treatments should be strictly applied to prevent amputation. Further clinical studies are needed to support the existing evidence regarding the clinical benefit of new approaches for the treatment of diabetic ulcers, and these approaches should be used only as add-on therapies to the gold-standard wound care. As a result, we see that EGF works in our case. However, we recommend further studies on EGF in the literature.

Disclosure Statement

There were no financial support or relationships between the authors and any organization or professional bodies that could pose any conflict of interests.

Competing Interests

Written informed consent obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images.

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